

SOIL CARBON MONITORING

If properly monitored all over the EU, new emissions on the order of 70MtCO₂ye⁻¹ could appear in croplands.

IDENTIFYING NEW AREAS

As long as soil carbon is not properly monitored, it will not be possible to identify the priority areas where new removals can be targeted and incentivized.

SUBSTANTIAL POTENTIAL IN THE EU

ROAD4SCHEMES - According to existing large-scale assessments in the EU, the soil carbon storage potential could add up to 150–350MtCO₂yr⁻¹

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SOIL CARBON THE BLIND SPOT OF EUROPEAN NATIONAL GHG INVENTORIES

Land-related climate policy

Most soil carbon stock *changes* in European soils are currently not being monitored, nor are they reported. This is a critical blind spot of land-related climate policy.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply.

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ scientists, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FUNDED PROJECT ROAD4SCHEMES

The aim is to assess strengths, weaknesses, and different perceptions of current strategies and schemes for carbon farming.

KEY WORDS: Carbon farming, result-based schemes, Ecosystem Services

PROJECT COORDINATOR

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Understanding how soil-carbon sequestration can contribute to climate change mitigation at the regional level and accounting for carbon.

Mission SOIL: conserve soil organic carbon stocks

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL funded project:
ROAD4SCHEMES

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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